

First steps in the development of a support application for Easy-to-Read adaptation

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Appendix A. Supplementary Data

This section presents the supplementary tables and figures to complete the content of the paper. Firstly, the tables reflect the data and graphs presented in the different sections. On the other hand, Fig. 1 and 2, depicted as scatter plots, show the ranking of design and layout (DL) guidelines and writing (W) guidelines, respectively, according to participant's responses, as we presented in Section 3.3. Each point on the plot represents a guideline (DLx or Wx); while its position on the graph means (a) the position in the ranking of guidelines to analyse E2R compliance (X axis) and (b) the position in the ranking of guidelines to recommend transformations of materials (Y axis).

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Table 1 Relationship between participants and the selected score values in both questions regarding identification and transformation. These statements in the questionnaire should be ranked from 1 to 5 based on how much the participant agrees with them (5 means that participant strongly agrees; 1 means that participant strongly disagrees).

Score Values	Participants	
	Identification	Transformation
1	0	0
2	1	0
3	0	2
4	7	6
5	26	26

Fig. 1 Design and Layout guidelines presented as a ranking in a scatter plot considering the selection of the participants in both choices -recommendation of transformation or diagnosis of materials.

Fig. 2 Writing guidelines presented as a ranking in a scatter plot considering the selection of the participants in both choices -recommendation of transformation or diagnosis of materials.

Table 2 Guidelines ranked according to the selection of the participants who consider that FACILE should address only the task related to the diagnosis of materials.

Diagnosis of Materials					
Design and Layout			Writing		
Guideline	Percentage	Ranking Position	Guideline	Percentage	Ranking Position
DL10. Minimum line spacing should be 1.5"	52,94%	1	W4. A colon (:) must be used when entering a list that enumerates more than three items or when entering a dialogue	44,12%	1
DL1. Text should be left-aligned	50,00%	2	W22. Sentences must have a subject	41,18%	2
DL3. Avoid hyphenating the words at the end of a line	44,12%	3	W2. Initial capital letters should be used at the beginning of a paragraph or title, after a full stop or in proper nouns	38,24%	3
DL7. Pictures cannot be separated between pages	41,18%	4	W21. Passive voice should be avoided	35,29%	
DL2. Text justification should be avoided	35,29%	5	W18. The text should be made up of short, simple sentences	35,29%	
DL5. Pictures should be placed close to the text	32,35%	6	W19. The use of pronouns must be correct	35,29%	4
DL9. The page number must be included on the outside of the page, at the bottom or at the top	29,41%	7	W11. The telephone numbers must be separated by blocks	35,29%	
DL6. Pictures must agree with the text and concretely depict what is described in the text	26,47%	8	W5. The semicolon (;) should not be used	35,29%	
DL8. Text written in portrait orientation should be avoided	26,47%		W6. Avoid the use of etcetera or ellipses	35,29%	
DL4. All pages of the document must have the same orientation (landscape or portrait)	23,53%	9	W14. Passive reflexive should be avoided	32,35%	
			W3. The full stop must be replaced by a new paragraph or by a conjunction	32,35%	5
			W8. Adverbs ending in -mente (-ly in English) should be avoided	32,35%	
			W1. Do not capitalise words or phrases, except in the case of acronyms	26,47%	
			W16. The use of two or more consecutive verbs should be avoided, except for periphrases with the modal verbs	26,47%	6
			W10. The use of words with undefined content such as: thing, something or subject should be avoided	26,47%	
			W9. Superlatives should be avoided	26,47%	
			W17. The use of complex connectors between sentences, such as therefore, nevertheless or consequently should be avoided	23,53%	
			W15. If possible, the use of sentences with gerunds should be avoided	23,53%	7
			W13. Avoid writing the time in 24-hour format	23,53%	
			W20. The text must be written in the second person	20,59%	
			W12. The use of fractions and percentages should be avoided	20,59%	8
			W7. Inverted commas should not be used (Spanish «» or English " ")	14,71%	9

Table 3 Guidelines ranked according to the selection of the participants who consider that FACILE should address only the task related to the transformation of materials.

Transformation					
Design and Layout			Writing		
Guideline	Percentage	Ranking Position	Guideline	Percentage	Ranking Position
DL9. The page number must be included on the outside of the page, at the bottom or at the top	32,35%	1	W20. The text must be written in the second person	29,41%	1
DL2. Text justification should be avoided	23,53%	2	W7. Inverted commas should not be used (Spanish «» or English " ")	29,41%	
DL6. Pictures must agree with the text and concretely depict what is described in the text	20,59%	3	W17. The use of complex connectors between sentences, such as therefore, nevertheless or consequently should be avoided	26,47%	
DL4. All pages of the document must have the same orientation (landscape or portrait)	20,59%		W10. The use of words with undefined content such as: thing, something or subject should be avoided	26,47%	2
DL1. Text should be left-aligned	17,65%	4	W13. Avoid writing the time in 24-hour format	26,47%	
DL8. Text written in portrait orientation should be avoided	17,65%		W9. Superlatives should be avoided	26,47%	
DL3. Avoid hyphenating the words at the end of a line	14,71%	5	W16. The use of two or more consecutive verbs should be avoided, except for periphrases with the modal verbs	23,53%	3
DL5. Pictures should be placed close to the text	14,71%		W15. If possible, the use of sentences with gerunds should be avoided	20,59%	
DL7. Pictures cannot be separated between pages	11,76%	6	W12. The use of fractions and percentages should be avoided	20,59%	4
DL10. Minimum line spacing should be 1.5"	8,82%	7	W3. The full stop must be replaced by a new paragraph or by a conjunction	20,59%	
			W8. Adverbs ending in -mente (-ly in English) should be avoided	20,59%	
			W21. Passive voice should be avoided	17,65%	
			W11. The telephone numbers must be separated by blocks	17,65%	5
			W6. Avoid the use of etcetera or ellipses	17,65%	
			W18. The text should be made up of short, simple sentences	14,71%	
			W5. The semicolon (;) should not be used	14,71%	6
			W1. Do not capitalise words or phrases, except in the case of acronyms	14,71%	
			W4. A colon (:) must be used when entering a list that enumerates more than three items or when entering a dialogue	14,71%	
			W19. The use of pronouns must be correct	11,76%	
			W14. Passive reflexive should be avoided	11,76%	7
			W2. Initial capital letters should be used at the beginning of a paragraph or title, after a full stop or in proper nouns	11,76%	
			W22. Sentences must have a subject	5,88%	8

Table 4 Guidelines ranked according to the selection of the participants who consider that FACILE should address both tasks at the same time: the E2R analysis and the subsequent transformation.

Both (Diagnosis of Materials and Transformation)					
Design and Layout			Writing		
Guideline	Percentage	Ranking Position	Guideline	Percentage	Ranking Position
DL6. Pictures must agree with the text and concretely depict what is described in the text	35,29%	1	W14. Passive reflexive should be avoided	38,24%	1
DL5. Pictures should be placed close to the text	32,35%	2	W19. The use of pronouns must be correct	35,29%	2
DL7. Pictures cannot be separated between pages	26,47%	3	W22. Sentences must have a subject	35,29%	2
DL3. Avoid hyphenating the words at the end of a line	26,47%		W21. Passive voice should be avoided	32,35%	
DL10. Minimum line spacing should be 1.5"	26,47%	5	W1. Do not capitalise words or phrases, except in the case of acronyms	29,41%	4
DL8. Text written in portrait orientation should be avoided	26,47%		W12. The use of fractions and percentages should be avoided	29,41%	
DL4. All pages of the document must have the same orientation (landscape or portrait)	26,47%		W13. Avoid writing the time in 24-hour format	29,41%	
DL9. The page number must be included on the outside of the page, at the bottom or at the top	23,53%	6	W18. The text should be made up of short, simple sentences	26,47%	5
DL2. Text justification should be avoided	20,59%	7	W11. The telephone numbers must be separated by blocks	26,47%	
DL1. Text should be left-aligned	17,65%	8	W7. Inverted commas should not be used (Spanish « » or English " ")	26,47%	
			W17. The use of complex connectors between sentences, such as therefore, nevertheless or consequently should be avoided	26,47%	
			W15. If possible, the use of sentences with gerunds should be avoided	26,47%	
			W5. The semicolon (;) should not be used	23,53%	
			W6. Avoid the use of etcetera or ellipses	23,53%	
			W16. The use of two or more consecutive verbs should be avoided, except for periphrases with the modal verbs	23,53%	6
			W3. The full stop must be replaced by a new paragraph or by a conjunction	23,53%	
			W8. Adverbs ending in -mente (-ly in English) should be avoided	23,53%	7
			W10. The use of words with undefined content such as: thing, something or subject should be avoided	20,59%	
			W2. Initial capital letters should be used at the beginning of a paragraph or title, after a full stop or in proper nouns	20,59%	
			W9. Superlatives should be avoided	20,59%	
			W4. A colon (:) must be used when entering a list that enumerates more than three items or when entering a dialogue	20,59%	
			W20. The text must be written in the second person	14,71%	8